

NATIONAL MECHANISMS FOR STIMULATING THE PARTICIPATION OF REPRESENTATIVES OF NATIONAL MINORITIES IN THE ELECTORAL PROCESS

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Abstract. The article analyzes the following main directions of legal regulation for the participation of national minorities in political life: the system of granting advantages when participating in elections, quotas of seats in parliament, the establishment of proportions of representation of various ethnic groups in parliament, voting in parliament, taking into account the opinions of ethnic groups, the adoption of special legislative acts aimed at protecting the rights of representatives of national minorities, establishment of institutions of commissioners for the rights of national minorities, granting special privileges to autonomies, giving compatriots the opportunity to participate in elections.

Key words: national mechanisms, incentives for participation, representatives of national minorities, electoral process.

Аннотация. Мақолада миллий озчиликларнинг сиёсий ҳаётдаги иштирокини ҳуқуқий тартибга солишнинг қуйидаги асосий йўналишлари таҳлил қилинган: сайловларда иштирок этишда имтиёзлар бериш тизими, парламентдаги депутатлик ўринларини квоталаш, парламентдаги турли этник гуруҳлар вакиллик нисбатини белгилаш, этник гуруҳларнинг фикрларини инobatга олган ҳолда парламентда овоз бериш, миллий озчиликлар вакилларининг ҳуқуқларини ҳимоя қилишга қаратилган махсус қонун ҳужжатларини қабул қилиш, миллий озчиликлар ҳуқуқлари бўйича ваколатли институтларни жорий этиш, мухториятларга алоҳида имтиёзлар бериш, ватандошларга сайловларда қатнашиш имкониятини тақдим этиш ва чет элдаги миллий диаспораларни қўллаб-қувватлаш.

Калит сўзлар: миллий механизмлар, иштирокни рағбатлантириш, миллий озчиликлар вакиллари, сайлов жараёни.

Аннотация. В статье анализируются следующие основные направления правового регулирования участия национальных меньшинств в политической жизни: система предоставления преимуществ при участии в выборах, квотирование мест в парламенте, установление пропорций представительства различных этнических групп в парламенте, голосование в парламенте с учетом мнения этнических групп, принятие специальных законодательных актов, направленных на защиту прав представителей национальных меньшинств, учреждение институтов уполномоченных по правам национальных меньшинств, предоставление особых привилегий автономиям, предоставление возможности участвовать в выборах соотечественникам, поддержка национальных диаспор за рубежом.

Ключевые слова: национальные механизмы, стимулирования участия, представители национальных меньшинств, избирательный процесс.

The proclamation in international instruments of the principle of equality, political rights and the prohibition of discrimination, including on ethnic grounds, creates a certain legal basis for the participation of national minorities in political life on an equal basis with the main ethnic group. However, as a rule, they have different opportunities, and formal equality which ensures the absence of only the most severe forms of discrimination on ethnic grounds. Significant differences in the social status and opportunities of various ethnic groups are reproduced, including in the political sphere, due to the inertia of social processes, the difficulties of the existence of minorities under the domination of a different and state-supported culture, prejudice against minorities and often insufficient material resources.

Access of national minorities to the political establishment is provided, as a rule, by special measures and efforts, both informal and established by normative acts. If we talk about informal opportunities for political participation, then political parties of national minorities increase their chances of representation by cooperating with national parties. For example, in Austria, some Slovenian party organizations conclude pre-election agreements with national parties. It should be noted, however, that informal institutions do not always ensure the interests of national minorities (in particular, because the desire on both sides is needed to conclude such agreements).

In this sense, the formalization of the participation of national minorities is not only preferable for the latter, but is often the only way to ensure their political participation. Legal mechanisms for "equalizing opportunities" to ensure the participation of national minorities and the protection of their interests can be created both at the stage of the electoral process and in the Parliament itself.

According to G. Andreeva, the system of granting advantages when participating in elections consists, first of all, in freeing national minority parties from fulfilling the requirements that block the way to parliament for small parties¹. This practice exists, for example, in Germany. According to p. 6 of paragraph 6 of the Federal Election Law, when allocating seats ac-

ording to land lists, only those parties that received at least five percent of all valid second votes cast in Germany are taken into account (in Germany, every voter in federal elections receives two votes: the first for voting in the electoral district, the second for voting on national electoral lists) or have received a deputy mandate in at least three electoral districts. However, this provision does not apply to lists submitted by national minority parties. Similar provisions exist in some land election laws. It should be noted, however, that there is no uniform policy and principles of legislation at the federal and land levels. Thus, the Constitution of the State of Schleswig-Holstein contains quite detailed provisions on the national minorities of the Danes and Frisians, however, according to the land electoral law, only the Danish minority is completely exempt from the five percent barrier².

In Saxony, two articles of the Constitution are devoted to the protection of minorities, and Article 5 distinguishes between minorities who have German citizenship, who are guaranteed protection, and foreign minorities whose interests "will be respected". Article 6 is devoted to the rights of the national minority of the Sorbs, but the parties and party associations of the Sorbs are not exempt from the requirements of the five percent barrier.

The Brandenburg Constitution has a special article entitled "The rights of the Sorbs" (Article 25), which contains guarantees from the state to ensure the cultural autonomy of the Sorbs, "the actual political participation of the Sorbs people", including law-making, requirements for the law regulating the legal status of the Sorbs, as well as the norm on the use of the Sorbs language in the places of residence of the Sorbs and a description of the colors of the Sorbian flag³. In this land, an exemption from the five percent barrier has been established for sorbs. There are small groups of Frisian speakers in Lower Saxony, but Lower Saxon legislation does not grant them any special status. Thus, the land legislation reflects other concepts of minorities that differ from the federal level. In German literature it is noted that in this way the State guarantees different rights to different minority groups, and in this connection, there is a problem of

¹ Андреева Г. Правовые формы участия национальных меньшинств в политической жизни (обзор зарубежного опыта) // Материк. Бюллетень № 81, 83. 2003 г.

² https://no-regime.com/ru-deru/wiki/Verfassung_des_Landes_Schleswig-Holstein

³ <https://cyberleninka.ru/article/n/osobennosti-konstitutsionnogo-protsess-a-v-subekte-federatsii-na-primere-konstitutsionnogo-sudazemli-brandenburg>.

linking the policy towards national minorities with the principle of equality.

Another way to ensure the representation of national minorities who, due to their small number, cannot get into Parliament on a general basis, is through quotas. The institution of quotas in the electoral process is a phenomenon that is quite common in world law enforcement practice. In foreign countries, there are quotas for representatives from national minorities, civil society institutions, women and presidential quotas. Thus, legislative quotas for representatives of national minorities in parliament are provided for by the legislation of 52 countries. Legislative quotas (from 1 to 10 seats) for representatives of national minorities in the lower house of Parliament are provided in 35 countries, including Belgium, Denmark, India, Iran, Italy, Kazakhstan, China, Pakistan, Portugal, Croatia, Romania, Slovenia, Serbia, Finland, etc⁴.

Quotas for national minorities in the upper house of Parliament are provided for by the laws of 17 countries of the world.

Legislative quotas for women have been introduced in 24 countries.

In Belgium, out of 71 members of the Senate, 21 are elected by the Councils of the Flemish, French and German-speaking Communities.

In the UK, 26 members of the House of Lords are religious figures.

In Slovenia, quotas have been set for members of the upper house - the National Council:

- 22 – for representatives of local interests;
- 6 – for representatives of non-profit organizations;
- 4 – for representatives of employers;
- 4 – for workers' representatives and
- 4 – for farmers and independent trade unions.

In accordance with the amendments and additions to the electoral legislation of the Republic of Kazakhstan (2007) in Kazakhstan, nine out of 107 seats in the Majilis (the Lower House of Parliament) belong to the Assembly of the People of Kazakhstan, which includes representatives of 130 ethnic groups professing 45 confessions⁵.

It is believed that the quota system to a certain extent contradicts the liberal tradition, but in some cases their use is inevitable. For example, in India, 2 seats are traditionally reserved for representatives of

the Anglo-Indian community, who, due to their small number, would not be represented in a country with a billion population. Of the recently introduced quotas, Belgium can be noted. At the constitutional level, it is established that a certain part of senators from different linguistic groups must live on election day in the bilingual region of Brussels-the capital.

Thus, ethnic balance is ensured in the representation. Quotas are also used in some post-socialist states. Thus, in Slovenia, the autochthonous Italian and Hungarian national communities are guaranteed a number of political rights, including with regard to political representation. Article 64 of the Slovenian Constitution of 1991 states: "National communities are directly represented in representative bodies of local self-government and in Parliament." This norm in relation to the national parliament is specified in Article 80, according to which "one deputy from the Italian and Hungarian national communities is always elected to the National Assembly." There is a legislative regulation of the participation of ethnic and national communities and minorities in Croatia. For national and ethnic minorities numbering less than eight percent of the population of the republic, a quota of five parliamentary seats has been established (the remaining minorities must be represented in proportion to the number).

Close to quotas is such a way of ensuring the political representation of minorities as the legislative establishment of the proportions of representation of various ethnic groups in Parliament. He was elected, for example, in Cyprus. According to Article 62 of the 1960 Constitution, of the 50 deputies who make up the Parliament, 70 percent are elected by the Greek community, and 30 by the Turkish community from representatives of each community separately.

Belgium has also followed the path of establishing proportions, and in this country the proportion is maintained with the help of a rather complex system of forming a representative body. If the House of Representatives in this country is formed on a proportional basis, then the Senate is formed in three ways: forty senators are elected by electoral colleges (25 of them by the Dutch electoral college, 15 by the French); Twenty-one are appointed by the Councils of the Communities (10 by the Council of the Flemish Com-

⁴ <https://cyberleninka.ru/article/n/natsiya-i-natsionalnye-mensinstva-v-parlamentah-ot-xx-k-xxi-veku>.

⁵ <https://legalns.com/download/books/cons/slovenia.pdf>.

munity, 10 by the Council of the French Community and 1 by the Council of the German-Speaking Community) and ten are appointed by the senators mentioned above.

The same principle of proportionality was the basis for the formation of the Parliamentary Assembly of the Republic of Bosnia and Herzegovina in 1995, according to Article IV of the Constitution, the Chamber of Peoples has 15 deputies (five Croats, five Bosniaks and five Serbs).

The fact that a minority got into parliament does not guarantee that its interests are really taken into account. This only means that it can "voice" its interests from the parliamentary rostrum, which is important, but often not enough to solve the problems of minorities. In order for the political representation of national minorities to gain real content, special mechanisms should be developed to ensure their interests in the form of certain parliamentary procedures. Depending on the specifics of representation in a given country, they may relate to different aspects of parliamentary procedure: quorum, ensuring the representation of minorities in the leadership of parliament, the composition of commissions, etc.).

It is possible, for example, to establish such a quorum requirement in the regulations, in which a representative body will be able to start work only in the presence of representatives of national minorities. Such a legal mechanism is laid down in the Constitution of Bosnia and Herzegovina, according to Article IV of which the quorum in the Chamber of Peoples is three Bosnian, three Serbian and three Croatian deputies.

In addition, parliamentary procedures should guarantee the representation of national minorities in various internal bodies of Parliament (presidium, bureau, commissions, etc.). This practice exists in a number of countries.

In Cyprus, for example, it is established that the Chairman of the House of Representatives is a Greek elected by deputies from the Greek community, and the deputy chairman is a Turk elected by deputies from the Turkish community. They are elected separately, during the same meeting, at the beginning of the session and for the entire term of office of the House of Representatives (Article 72 of the 1960 Constitution). In the event of their temporary absence or the incomplete procedure for filling a vacant position, their functions are performed by the oldest depu-

ty of the relevant community, except in the case when the deputies of this community decide otherwise. The Constitution also stipulates that two Greeks and one Turk are appointed to the positions of Secretaries of the House of Representatives, and there is a similar regulation regarding the position of observers of the House of Representatives. With regard to the composition of the commissions of the House of Representatives, a general principle has been formulated: "Greek and Turkish community groups, as well as political party groups existing in the House of Representatives, should be represented in all permanent commissions, in extraordinary commissions drawn up for a specific task, or in special commissions of the Chamber. In total, however, the number of members of such commissions, representing, respectively, deputies elected by the Greek and Turkish communities, must correspond to the proportion that takes place in the distribution of parliamentary seats in the House of Representatives between deputies elected, respectively, by the Greek and Turkish communities" (Part 4 of Article 73 of the Constitution).

Another important point for ensuring the participation of national minorities in political decision-making is voting in Parliament, taking into account the views of ethnic groups.

The most well-known method in this regard is the separate voting of representatives of different ethnic communities. At the same time, in the most democratic version, a decision is made if it is approved by all communities by a majority vote in each of them. For example, in the representative body of the Italian region Trentino-Alto Adige/South Tyrol, voting is carried out on the majority of members of linguistic groups.

In Cyprus, a general procedure has been established at the constitutional level, according to which laws and resolutions of the House of Representatives (Parliament of the country) are approved by a simple majority of the deputies present and voting. However, any amendment to the electoral law, the approval of a law relating to municipalities, and any law establishing taxes or duties require a separate simple majority of the deputies participating in the vote, elected respectively by the Greek and Turkish communities (Article 78 of the 1960 Constitution of Cyprus).

In Bosnia and Herzegovina, there is a rather complicated procedure for making decisions and coordinating the positions of deputies from each of the en-

tities. Paragraph 3d of Article IV establishes that all decisions in both Chambers are taken by a majority of those present and voting. Deputies of the House of Peoples or members of the House of Representatives do everything in their power to ensure that this majority includes at least one third of the votes of deputies or members from the territory of each Entity (the Republic of Bosnia and Herzegovina consists of two entities: the Federation of Bosnia and Herzegovina and the Republika Srpska). If the majority of votes does not include a third of the votes of deputies of the House of Peoples or members of the House of Representatives of the territory of each Entity, then the Chairman and Vice-Chairmen form a commission and seek approval within three days from the moment of voting. If these efforts are unsuccessful, decisions are taken by a majority of those present and voting, provided that the number of those voting against does not include two-thirds or more of the deputies of the House of Peoples or members of the House of Representatives elected from each Entity.

According to the Belgian Constitution of 1994, on the contrary, all decisions in Parliament are taken by an absolute majority of votes, with the exception of those established by the rules of procedure of the Chambers regarding elections and the presentation of candidates. In case of a split vote, the proposal put to the vote is rejected. None of the Chambers can make decisions unless a majority of its members have gathered. In this country, such a parliamentary institution as a resolution is used to ensure the interests of ethnic communities. According to Article 54 of the Constitution, "a reasoned resolution signed by at least three-quarters of the members of one of the linguistic groups and submitted after the submission of the report, before the final vote in a public meeting, may be announced that the provisions of the draft law or the proposal of the law specified in the resolution, with the exception of budget laws, as well as laws that are adopted by a qualified majority, are capable of causing serious damage to relations between communities".

Accordingly, it can be stated that the parliamentary procedure is suspended in this case, and the resolution is submitted to the Council of Ministers, which within thirty days submits its opinion on the resolu-

tion or on a bill or a proposal of a law with possible amendments. With regard to this procedure, there is a significant restriction against abuse of it: it can be applied no more than once by members of the same linguistic group in relation to the same bill or proposal of the law

A similar procedure is established in the Constitution of Bosnia and Herzegovina of 1995. According to paragraphs 3e and 3f of Article IV, the proposed decision of the Parliamentary Assembly may be declared detrimental to the vital interests of the Bosnian, Serbian or Croatian peoples by the majority of Bosnian, Serbian or Croatian deputies. For the approval of such a proposed decision in the Chamber of Peoples, a majority of Bosnian, Serbian or Croatian deputies present and voting is required. If the majority of Bosnian, Serbian or Croatian deputies object to the application of this rule, the Chairman of the Chamber of Peoples immediately convenes a joint commission consisting of three deputies, who are elected by Bosnian, Serbian or Croatian deputies, respectively, to resolve this issue. If the commission fails to resolve the issue within five days, it is referred to the Constitutional Court, which promptly examines it for compliance with the procedure⁶.

In some countries, special parliamentary committees and commissions have been established for detailed consideration and discussion of issues affecting the interests of national minorities (Austria, Albania, Hungary, etc.).

The state-legal instruments of political participation developed by world practice protect the rights of national minorities to one degree or another under any more or less democratic regime. Naturally, the more democratic the country's political regime is, the more developed the culture of tolerance and respect for human rights in society, the more effectively ethno-national conflicts are prevented and resolved. In this case, the use of legal means becomes not only a way to protect the rights of national minorities, but also provides alternative political solutions, increases the flexibility of the public administration system and thereby multiplies its effectiveness. This means that by ensuring the rights of minorities, including by legal means, the state acquires a new modern quality that meets the challenges of the time.

⁶ https://www.un.org/ru/documents/decl_conv/conventions/pdf/constitution.pdf.